

Spatially and time-resolved carrier dynamics in core-shell InGaN/GaN multiple-quantum wells on GaN wire

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ABSTRACT: Time-resolved cathodoluminescence is a key tool for the investigation of carrier recombination phenomena in semiconductor nanostructures with high temporal and spatial resolution. In such experiments, an electron pulse usually excites several decay channels in a nanostructure at once. However, optical spectroscopic information can be also extracted using pulses from a synchrotron storage ring in a hard X-ray nanoprobe, exploiting a phenomenon called X-ray excited optical luminescence. With a broad energy range, this approach offers several advantages in terms of hyperspectral imaging and *in-situ* capabilities, enabling the understanding of multiple property-function relationships at the nanometer scale. Here, we applied this technique with a time resolution of 20 picoseconds and a spatial resolution of 80

nanometers to study carrier dynamics in individual core-shell InGaN/GaN multiple quantum well heterostructures deposited on GaN wires. Our findings suggest that the dynamics in single GaN/InGaN MQW wires is governed by the m -plane related MQW states, where carrier capture and recombination takes place on the picosecond timescales. Our results also support previous experimental findings for carrier localization phenomena at the hexagon apex of the wire. The carrier decay rates strongly depend on the spatial indium incorporation in the MQWs and on the defects associated with each facet. Further studies can cover not only the profiling of charge dynamic processes, but also the mapping of the radiative recombination of nonequilibrium carriers in more complex systems with competing optical channels. Its great potential becomes more valuable when this approach is used in conjunction with other methods, such as X-ray absorption spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction. Finally, our experiment calls for further investigations on the underlying mechanisms of optoelectronic nanodevices.

The performance of semiconductor nanodevices is critically governed by the charge transfer dynamics.[1] For example, the high speed on–off operation in GaN-based light-emitting diodes (LEDs) is limited by long carrier lifetimes in the *c*-plane direction caused by spontaneous and piezoelectric polarizations. [2] Recently, this major barrier has been overcome using *m*-plane core–shell InGaN/GaN wire LEDs, where the absence of quantum confined Stark-effect (QCSE) reduces the carrier recombination lifetimes. [3] Ultrafast times in the picosecond timescale have been reported, [4,5] which are at least one to two orders of magnitude shorter than those obtained for *c*-plane InGaN/GaN quantum wells (~ 1.5 ns at 300 K). [6] Similar values between 21–35 ps have been found for coaxial, polarization-free InGaN/GaN multi-quantum wells (MQWs) wire heterostructures at 300 K. [7,8] In addition, carrier decay rates that deviate from the single-exponential behaviors were revealed, [9] indicating multiple carrier localization effects present in InGaN/GaN core–shell MQWs heterostructures. [10] So far, the ultrafast carrier dynamical properties have been commonly studied using spatially averaged measurements, which mask the rich variety of charge transfer phenomena and carrier recombination kinetics originated from nanosized heterogeneities. While ensembles of wires are often investigated by time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL), [11,12] to date only little attention has been paid to the carrier decay rates from single wires using more sophisticated approaches, like time-resolved cathodoluminescence (TRCL) [13] and ultrafast optical microscopy. [14] Alternatively, to extract spectroscopic information in the spatio-temporal domain, we could also make use of scanning near-field optical microscopy (SNOM) equipped with a short-pulsed laser [15] and micro-electroluminescence through the probe of scanning tunneling microscope. [16] However, most of these techniques suffer from critical constraints such as restrictions to surfaces or to small areas in the region within ~ 10 nm of the tip or nano-antenna. By the way, through ultrafast optical microscopy the intraband carrier-carrier scattering was revealed to be the main channel governing carrier capture in InGaN/GaN core-

shell heterostructures, whereas subsequent carrier relaxation was dominated by three-carrier Auger recombination at higher densities and bimolecular recombination at lower densities. [14] Although most optoelectronic applications benefit from ensembles of wires, their inherent optical properties are critically determined by the local structural fluctuations present in individual wires. [4,17] Apart from variations in terms of diameter, length and shape, nanoscale defects in single wires can notably impact the effective performance because manifold optical processes and decay channels are induced by the spatial separation of photoexcited charges. It is well known that the InGaN/GaN core-shell QWs often suffer from nanosized inhomogeneities generated by the growth kinetics.[18,19] Fabrication imperfections result in indium fluctuations within InGaN wells, formation of dot-like In-rich clusters, voids and well width deviations, all of them dependent on the chemical deposition along the wire.[20,21] Moreover, a high density of basal stacking faults as well as mixed polarity domains are commonly observed in these core-shell wires. [22,23] Therefore, understanding how defects and heterogeneities affect carrier capture, relaxation, transport and recombination pathways at high spatial resolution remains quite challenging.

Here, in an effort to address this issue, we apply time-resolved X-ray excited optical luminescence (TRXEOL) microscopy to investigate ultrafast picosecond carrier dynamics in core-shell InGaN/GaN MQWs deposited on GaN wires.[24,25] With 50 ps time resolution, our experimental arrangement exploits a hard X-ray nanobeam (80 nm) and uses time-correlated single-photon counting with an avalanche photodiode. [26] Hard X-ray nanoprobe combines the great ability of a scanning probe microscopy to resolve nanoscale features with trace elemental sensitivity using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy.[27] Despite the common concepts shared with TRCL, the TRXEOL approach offers several advantages: i) larger depth resolved capability; ii) no need to operate under high vacuum conditions, which limits the use of *in-situ* environment setups, or need of challenging sample preparation that can even modify

the intrinsic sample properties; iii) multimode imaging capabilities that enable the correlation of the optical properties (via XEOL) with the compositional distribution (XRF) at the nanometer scale (as well as potentially structural information by X-ray diffraction or X-ray absorption techniques); iv) superior elemental detection limits (below ppb levels); v) chemical site selectivity; vi) tunable pulsed structure; and vii) orientation effects by polarization selection rules. In this context, a recent TRXEOL system has been further developed as well in the hard X-ray nanoprobe 23A at the Taiwan Photon Source using a streak camera that is coupled to the light spectrometer. [28] At macroscopic length scales, conventional XEOL layouts can be found in several synchrotron radiation facilities, like the Canadian Light Source, Advanced Photon Source, Cornell High Energy Synchrotron Source and Diamond Light Source. [29-31]

The present work reveals the critical role played by the disorder/In content in the spatial variation of the decay rates along the core-shell InGaN/GaN MQWs wire. Our findings show the need to go beyond spatially averaged time-resolved acquisitions to understand the impact of material heterogeneities on the elementary carrier recombination channels. As a result, we report additional insights into the nature of the fast carrier response phenomena in single InGaN/GaN core-shell wires.

Figure 1. Schematic of experimental setup. The X-ray nanobeam impinges on the sample, which emits light and X-ray fluorescence photons. X-ray excited optical luminescence and X-ray fluorescence spectra are recorded with a far-field optics system and a Si drift detector, respectively, for each raster position of the sample. A cross-sectional view highlighting the deposition of the nonpolar *m*-plane and polar *c*-plane GaN/InGaN MQWs is included in the figure.

Figure 1 (a) shows a schematic of the experimental arrangement used to obtain spatially and temporally resolved information at room temperature in air: a pulsed and intense hard X-ray beam from the storage ring is firstly pre-focused horizontally by a beamline Si mirror and then by a pair of Kirkpatrick-Baez Si mirrors down to nanometer scales [$100 \times 100 \text{ nm}^2$ spot size (V x H) with 10^{12} ph/s at 29.6 keV]. [26] The sample mounted in a piezo-stage is raster scanned in the hard X-ray nanobeam, while collecting simultaneously the emission of the characteristic secondary X-rays (XRF) using an energy dispersive Si drift detector and the X-ray excited optical luminescence (XEOL) by a far-field optical system. The timing structure of the 16 bunch filling mode of the storage ring [5.68 MHz repetition frequency and 50 ps pulse duration] is exploited to investigate ultrafast carrier dynamics, energy transfer processes and optical phenomena in the spatio-temporal domain. The XEOL is collected in a tilted angular geometry using a high numerical aperture lens. The light is then focused into a multimode optical fibre, which brings the XEOL signal out of the experimental hutch. Once in the detection bench, the fibre can be connected to different spectrometers and detectors to analyse the XEOL signal in the spectral and time regimes. [24] For time resolved-XEOL (TR-XEOL) data acquisition, the luminescence emitted by the sample and collected by the XEOL optical head is dispersed by an 0.3 m focal length spectrometer (Acton) and detected by a Si avalanche photodiode (id100 from id-Quantique). Time correlated single photon counting electronics (PicoHarp 400 from PicoQuant) is applied to record the TR-XEOL decay curves. The impulse response function (IRF) of the TRXEOL arrangement is recorded using the visible part of the synchrotron light

under the same experimental conditions. After numerical deconvolution, it allows us to determine decay times with high signal to noise ratio and a time resolution superior than 20 ps. So far, there are just a few hard X-ray nanoprobe worldwide with such advanced capabilities to probe optical carrier dynamics processes with picosecond time and nanometer spatial resolutions.[27,28] Using several beam bunch modes, Lin *et al.* have successfully developed TRXEOL based on a streak camera with a 60nm spot size at the X-ray nanoprobe beamline 23A located at the Taiwan Photon Source. [28]

As a proof of concept, here we have applied this methodology to the hexagonal n-GaN/In_xGa_{1-x}N/n-GaN wires shown Figure 1 (b). The schematic highlights the cross section of the deposited InGaN/GaN multi-quantum well (MQW) core-shell nanowire heterostructures. The coaxial light-emitting diode (LED)-based heterostructure grown by metalorganic vapour phase epitaxy (MOVPE) consists of an inner n-doped GaN core (~2 μm diameter) with five periods of InGaN/GaN MQWs shell (1.25-nm-thick InGaN well with ~15% In concentration and 10-nm-thick GaN barrier).[32] The InGaN MWQs are deposited in both top *c*-plane and side *m*-plane facets, leading to strongly confined energy levels that provide high efficient traps for carriers. To collect the XEOL and XRF maps, the wires are detached from the substrate and then dispersed on silicon nitride membranes (Silson Ltd.). In general, the core-shell nanowire architecture exhibits notable advantages over planar group-III nitride structures in terms of optical performance. They display a high tolerance to lattice mismatched substrates with a much lower density of dislocations along the wires, as well as a large increase of the active area that limits the efficiency droop thanks to the fall of the current density. Additionally, they have a radial growth of nonpolar *m*-plane QWs, preventing quantum confined stark effects (QCSE) that hinders the overlapping of the electron and hole wavefunctions. Thus, a higher probability of radiative recombination also results into reduced carrier lifetimes, which can be used to develop flexible devices like LEDs, photodetectors and

GHz-range micro-LEDs for visible light communications at high frequencies (the modulation speed or the bandwidth is the inverse of the carrier recombination lifetime). [33]

Figure 2. Left panel: Average XEOL and XRF spectra taken from $\text{In}_{0.15}\text{Ga}_{0.85}\text{N}/\text{GaN}$ MQWs deposited on the polar top GaN core under two excitation configuration (top and side views). Right panel: XRF and XEOL maps collected with about 50 nm pixel size and 1second per point counting time, indicating the corresponding spatial distributions of major elements and principal light emission bands.

Figure 2 shows the hyperspectral results obtained by scanning a single wire along the radial and axial directions under different excitation configurations (top and side views). With a micrometer penetration depth, the hard X-ray nanobeam generates electrons and holes that then recombine via characteristic X-rays (XRF) or visible photons (XEOL). The photo-created carriers commonly diffuse within the GaN volume and/or become trapped by the MQWs layers. Thus, the concurrent acquisitions of XEOL and XRF identify the spatial distribution of

the recombination channels responsible for the radiative transitions and the elemental composition of the wire.

Let us start from the analysis of the XRF results and then the ones related to XEOL. Apart from the major elements, the average XRF spectrum reveals unintentional dopants (e.g., Cr, Fe and Ni) likely originated from the initial pattern formation and position-controlled selective MOVPE growth. The three-dimensional (3D) representation of the XRF data shows a high chemical contrast picture under the hexagonal cross-sectional geometry, which is indicative of uniform core-multishell encapsulation consistent with the targeted coaxial heterostructure (Fig. 2c-e). Within the length scale of the beam size, the indium related map taken from the top excitation configuration shows a homogeneous and controlled deposition of the InGaN layers, without signatures of deposition-induced diffusion and/or agglomeration effects at the corners. If indium fluctuations are present, then they are smaller than 100 nm. The incorporation of residual impurities does not alter the chemical modulation of the coaxial heterostructure; there is no evidence of substantial migration, formation of precipitates or clusters within the sensitivity of our experimental setup. On the other hand, the indium related pattern recorded from the sidewall excitation geometry shows an enhancement of the In signal at the edges of the wire, indicating a higher indium content if one assumes a uniform well width.

On the other hand, the average XEOL spectrum exhibits two principal light emission bands: a dominant large band at 2.16 eV assigned to the common yellow band (YB) emission from defects in GaN, and a weaker blue band located at 2.87 eV attributed to the radiative transitions from the InGaN/GaN MQWs. With a full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of about 200 meV, the light emission from the MQWs is weaker than from the GaN core due to mostly an excitation volume effect and, in a lesser degree, also the influence of nonradiative surface recombinations. Moreover, the shape of the luminescence spectra commonly depends on the excitation wavelength, excitation power, and temperature. Compared to standard

photoluminescence (PL) measurements, where it is possible to obtain luminescence spectra upon above-barrier and under-barrier excitations, by XEOL only above-barrier excitation is considered. Thus, there is no resonant excitation of carriers in the MQWs, but we do have an enhanced generation of carriers in the thick GaN core and barriers. With a nearly Gaussian shape and a FWHM of about 600 meV, the YB band is associated to the optical transition between the conduction band (or shallow donor) and deep acceptor with an activation energy of 0.8 – 0.9 eV. Its origin is still under debate; some researchers have ascribed the YB to Ga vacancies, whereas other authors have assigned it to carbon-related centers. [34] While the YB related map reveals a homogeneous distribution of the associated defects in the wire GaN core (which has the largest excited volume), the 3D projection of the emission attributed to the MQWs supports previous findings on carrier localization phenomena connected to the hexagonal geometry. [35] Although it might be possible that the carrier capture by defect related states in GaN (YB) suppresses extra recombination channels, the InGaN/GaN MQWs trap carriers and radiate light mainly from the vertices of the hexagon. This effect could again result from an enhanced carrier confinement in the regions where the MQWs merge and/or higher indium content localized at these edges. Such a brighter feature ascribed to confinement effects has been supported earlier through both experimental and theoretical works. [3, 35-38] On the contrary, some studies have reported a reduction in the luminescent intensity at the hexagon vertices associated to the incorporation of point defects, while the observation of a red-shift in their emission energy was assigned to an increase in the indium composition and potential nanoscale variations in strain.[39] Although we have not detected any preferential indium location at the hexagon vertices using the top excitation configuration but only at the edges of the sidewalls, some authors have predicted that indium accumulates and segregates at the outer corners of hexagonal rods due to the release of strain energy through local deformation at these points in the nanostructure. [39-41]

As a rule, two main emission peaks are often observed by cathodoluminescence (CL) at low temperatures from similar core-shell nanowire heterostructures:[3,42] 1) a short wavelength peak localized on the wire side facets that is commonly associated to the emission of the radial nonpolar m -plane MQWs, and 2) a long-wavelength peak assigned to the axial polar c -plane MQWs that arises only from the wire top facet. The light emission from the top c -plane facet is usually redshifted and weaker than the m -plane light emission because of QCSE. Moreover, the polar MQWs at the top of wires are usually wider and present higher indium concentration than the semipolar and nonpolar MQWs.[43] As a result, the c -plane MQWs related radiative recombination is shifted towards longer wavelengths because of the interplay of both indium content and strong QCSE in the polar MQWs.[44,45] According to a recent article about CL data taken on similar samples grown by the same research group, [13] the origin of the light emission coming from the MQWs at the wire top can be attributed to c -plane facets and/or to semipolar facets present at the junction between c -plane and m -plane surfaces. Owing to the common top surface roughening and mixed polarity, also the detection of the top facet light emission is often wire-to-wire dependent because of its random surface morphology related to the presence of different polarity domains. [23] In short, the radiative and non-radiative pathways strongly depend on the MQWs quality and on the defects associated with each facet.

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Figure 3. Left panel: Representative spatially resolved time decay spectra displaying the fitting results corresponding to the dominant decay rates. Right panel: Characteristic line profiles acquired along the white dotted lines represented in Figure 2.

Figure 3 displays several results: on the left part some representative TRXEOL measurements are displayed, while on the right part we plot characteristic line profiles acquired along the white dotted lines (represented in Figure 2). Whereas the gallium signal (blue square symbols) is pretty smooth in both axial and radial scans, the indium line profiles (yellow square symbols) reveal several points. In the axial scan, there is a superposition of the In contributions coming from the top and side facets, which results into a signal maximum at 200 nm. In the radial scan, assuming the well width does not vary, a higher indium content appears at the edges of the wire located at 500 and 2500 nm. Although our data do not have enough spatial resolution to detect

any In-compositional fluctuation that might take place at the atomic scale, in the linescan recorded along the axis of the wire, the constant indium signal between 400 and 1000 nm indicates a uniform In incorporation in that region. It is well known that the growth of core-shell InGaN MQWs on GaN wires very often suffers from alloys and layer thickness gradients along the length of the wire.[2,7,32,46,47] In particular, the observations of Kapoor *et al.* [13] in a similar series of samples have highlighted the In fluctuations in the MQWs probed by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) via energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) and by atom probe tomography (APT). Similarly, Messanvi *et al.* [48] attributed the red shifts detected in the CL maps to indium gradients along the core-shell region with more indium incorporated within the top part of the heterostructure.

Despite probing different sample depths, the integrated XEOL intensity of the two light emissions at 2.16 and 2.87 eV in a roughly proportional fashion follows the overall Ga and In elemental trends respectively, albeit affected by carrier transport phenomena; In terms of spatial localization, we do not observe an one-to-one correspondence between the elemental and optical profiles. Basically, the photocarriers are generated locally within the excitation volume of the hard X-ray nanobeam, but the optical luminescence is collected from much larger regions because of the diffusion processes of minority carriers and electron-hole pairs. Actually, similar effects are frequently exploited using CL to determine ambipolar diffusion lengths in core-shell nanowires. [49] Thus, the detected light spans not only radiative recombinations within the spot size excited by the X-ray nanobeam that also has a primary penetration depth, but also photogenerated carrier diffusion processes. Therefore, in the linescan the observed shift between the XEOL and XRF maxima of approximately 180 nm is driven by carrier motion phenomena. A fraction of electron-hole pairs, which are predominantly photogenerated in the GaN core, diffuses into the InGaN/GaN MQWs and recombine there in their confined energy levels via radiative transitions. Generally, alloy

composition and well width variations are considered as main sources of the potential fluctuations, but their impact on the emission broadening and carrier lifetimes may be different. On the other hand, the top left panel of Figure 3 illustrates the multi-exponential XEOL decay traces representative of the core GaN region (YB emission located 2.16 eV) and the InGaN MQWs (light emission centred at 2.87 eV). Usually, time-resolved PL (TRPL) reveals that nonradiative processes dominate at room temperature. Our results exhibit the presence of both rapidly and slowly decaying components. In order to estimate their particular contributions, the decay curves were approximated by the sum of two exponential functions: $I(t) = A_{\text{short}}e^{-t/\tau_{\text{short}}} + A_{\text{long}}e^{-t/\tau_{\text{long}}}$. [43] The value of $A \cdot \tau$ reflects the contribution of each component to the total XEOL signal (the amount of carriers participating in each decay process), since it equals to the integral of each term in the equation in the range from $t = 0$ to infinity. As expected, the estimated effective carrier lifetimes for both emission bands are very different. For the YB, the dominant contribution is represented by a slowly decaying component with decay times of about 3 ns, whereas for the MQWs the fast decaying component mostly contributes to the emission with decay times of about 100 ps. Another slower decay time is also present in the MQWs with much less weight. Within our experimental uncertainty, a fastest recombination rate is observed in the radial measurements (average ~ 90 ps) compared to the axial ones (average ~ 134 ps). This variation could come from the nature of the different facets (polar, semipolar or nonpolar) that contribute to the radiative recombination pathways, and/or from the nonradiative channels produced by defects present in the top facet (morphological and mixed polarity domains).[23] According to a recent review, [50,51] whereas on the c -plane tens of nanoseconds characterized typical PL decay times for polar MQWs, hundreds of picoseconds are commonly observed for semipolar and nonpolar MQWs. Moreover, previous TRPL reports also showed that the luminescence often decays by a nonexponential law in polar and semipolar QWs, while nonpolar QWs commonly display a

one-exponential decay. [52,53] The localization of electrons and holes due to the built-in electrostatic field and fluctuations of the MQWs potential connected with composition and thickness heterogeneities can be the reasons behind the non-exponential PL decay curves. [53] In summary, there are specific spectral and dynamical features that are commonly used as fingerprints to discriminate among the contributions to the luminescence from different types of InGaN MQWs: nonpolar, semipolar, and polar. Thus, in our scenario, the lengthened decay time in the axial scan compared to the radial one could be caused by the influence of defects in the recombinations from nonpolar and semipolar MQWs that control the carrier dynamics.

Figure 4. Left panel: Representative spatially resolved time decay spectra displaying the fitting results corresponding to the short and long decay components. Right panel: Spatial points carefully chosen to acquire the TRXEOL spectra shown in the left panel.

To provide more quantitative estimates on the carrier dynamic properties associated to the MQWs recombination channel located at 2.87 eV, we have excited the wire at carefully chosen

points labelled in Figure 4 with different colours. As it was already mentioned, following the signatures identified in Ref. [43] by Amano *et al.*, we could attribute the observed picosecond decay times to the recombination from semipolar and nonpolar MQWs. Indeed, the smaller QCSE present on these surfaces could lead to a stronger carrier wavefunction overlap, i.e. an enhanced radiative recombination rate. In particular, on the upper part of the figure, we show the decay curves recorded from the top facet (one point at the centre, two along the edges and two points onto the vertices – apex- of the hexagon prism). On the bottom part, the typical TRXEOL spectra collected along the sidewall facets as well as at the top of the wire are depicted. The sensitivity of our spatio-temporal approach is directly demonstrated by the differences observed among various transients. Full analysis of the data obtained by fitting through the bi-exponential function allows us to obtain a better understanding of the carrier dynamics. In general, from the decay signals, A_{short} is dominant all over compared to A_{long} , meaning that more carriers select the faster decay channel for radiative recombination. Although it is commonly accepted the two-step decay properties, so far the nature of both short and long decay processes are still under debate. For example, recently Lin *et al.* [54,55] have assigned the slow and fast luminescence dynamics to local indium fluctuations and InGaN thickness variation, respectively. On the other hand, in previous studies Sun *et al.* [56] concluded that, unlike slow decay associated to localization states, the fast decay might come from recombinations in extended states. Moreover, first reports by Feng *et al.* [57] attributed them to the carrier transport between different localized states by examining the wavelength-dependent and temperature-varying TRPL results together. Here, the faster (τ_{short}) and slower XEOL decay time (τ_{long}) constants obtained by fittings are listed in the figure. In good agreement with Figure 3, the decay times collected from sidewalls are generally shorter than the ones taken from the top surface. As it was already mentioned, the fast characteristic time of about $\tau_{\text{short}} \sim 100$ ps is typical of nonpolar and semipolar MQWs, where the reduced QCSE

enables more efficient radiative transitions. [58] If the assumptions of Lin *et al.* are valid (namely, the slow and fast decay times are connected to local indium fluctuations and InGaN thickness variations, respectively), [54,55] then our findings would suggest that in comparison to mild well thickness fluctuations (τ_{short}), in the top surface there are more significant In inhomogeneities (τ_{long}) than in the sidewalls. In particular, the short decay times are faster at the two vertices of the top surface, indicating a larger overlapping of the wavefunctions of the electrons and holes in these regions, which is consistent with their higher integrated XEOL intensity. Similarly, along the sidewall facets the short decay times are faster at the edges of the hexagon prism, supporting an enhancement of the radiative recombination rates given by superior quantum confinement effects. Summarizing, higher XEOL intensity and shorter fast decay rates are observed for the MQWs with higher indium content closer to the apex compared to the MQWs with lower indium fraction on the sidewalls of the wire heterostructure.

Figure 5. Left panel: Spatially resolved time decay spectra recorded along the axial scan represented in Figure 3 accompanied by corresponding XEOL emission. The fitting results corresponding to the short and long decay

components are included. Right panel: Characteristic profiles corresponding to elemental and XEOL relative intensities acquired along the axial direction.

In order to shed light on the radiative recombination pathways involved in the carrier dynamics within InGaN MQWs, a hyperspectral analysis is performed along the axial scan. Using our multi-imaging approach, Figure 5 enables to yield further insights into the role of local indium incorporation in the picosecond optical channels via correlations among the indium related intensity, optical decay times, spectral intensity, energy and linewidth variations. The MQWs emissions were fitted by Gaussian functions to obtain the spectral parameters. As it is shown by yellow square symbols, from the fitting results the XEOL characteristics (τ_{short} , τ_{long} , E , FWHM) present more or less pronounced gradients that follow the spatial shift driven by carrier diffusion phenomena in comparison to the elemental composition (as discussed above). Whereas the governing short decay time τ_{short} hardly changes from 131 ps at the wire top to 122 ps passing through a signal maximum of 144 ps (standard deviation $\sigma < 10$ ps), the long decay constant τ_{long} increases from 239 ps at the upper part of the wire to 339 ps with a stronger spatial variation up to 461 ps maximum ($\sigma \approx 74$ ps). Given the superposition of the signal contributions coming from the top and junction between c -plane and m -plane surfaces, the maxima observed in both decay times might result from the combined contribution of different planes, as well as imperfections, In heterogeneities, interface roughness and/or disorder present there. As it was pointed out, a higher density of morphological defects, In content and/or mixed polarity domains, which can act as nonradiative centres, might also affect the transition rates. Slower decay traces indicate a weaker oscillator strength, which should lead to a decrease in the radiative decay rate. Nevertheless, compared to the long decay time τ_{long} , the dominant short decay time τ_{short} looks less sensitive to varying spatial position. Moreover, the profile corresponding to τ_{long} effectively correlated with the gradients displayed by both 2.87 eV and indium relative intensities. In good agreement, from the wire top we further observe a slight

blueshift of the peak energy of the MQWs transition accompanied by a small reduction of the light emission linewidth (FWHM), [13] as it is commonly detected for such InGaN/GaN core-shell structures. [32,58,59] Following Lin *et al.* statements, which associated the long and short decay processes to local indium fluctuations and InGaN thickness variation respectively, our results along the axis scan would again indicate that the change in the well thickness (τ_{short}) could be less remarkable than that one related to the indium distribution (τ_{long}). Nanoscale fluctuations in the indium concentration close to the wire top, which were undetectable in this work, may produce both topological (structural) and energetic disorders in InGaN. [47] Carriers confined in different spatial regions could diffuse due to excitation from localized to excited levels (energetic disorder) or by hopping among localized states (topological disorder). Thus, the behaviour of the spectral broadening (i.e., maximum FWHM ≈ 224 meV close to the wire top) could be attributed to local indium distributions like those fluctuations observed by APT mappings, which are consistent with the intensity decrease along the axial scan. Likewise, the underlying mechanisms behind the observed redshift of the peak energy towards the wire top are the shortening of the effective band gap of the InGaN alloy with increasing In content, localized energy states associated to In inhomogeneities and the energy band tilt in InGaN MQWs due to a possible influence of piezoelectric polarizations from *c*-plane facets. [7,60] As a result, there are several carrier relaxation pathways governing the lengthened decay dynamics due to the strong disorder potential distribution of the carriers; The higher indium concentration and fluctuations in the InGaN MQWs close to the wire top rapidly decrease the transition rates via nonradiative recombinations, resulting in a reduced decay time and larger spectral characteristics.

In summary, we have developed an advanced spectroscopic tool that relies on a picosecond time-resolved XEOL microscope with a time resolution of about 20 ps, together with a spatial

resolution of 80 nm. This system allows us to study the carrier dynamics of individual core-shell InGaN/GaN heterostructured wires, and obtain a better understanding of the photoexcited carrier paths at nanoscales. Our findings suggest that well width fluctuations, compared to variations of InGaN alloy composition, play a minor role in the spatial dependent carrier dynamics. Further analysis of the decay rate from excited states as a function of excitation intensity, temperature and/or energy levels can provide extra information on carrier capture cross sections of the underlying recombination dynamics. More advanced improvements of this powerful tool for the analysis of nanostructure related states would include the use of cryogenic temperature and stream camera to quickly capture sharper and enhanced light emission phenomena, the exploitation of polarization dependent XEOL scheme to derive transients as a function of anisotropies, as well as maps of electronic properties with better spatial resolutions. Though readily accessible with current X-ray nanofocusing optics, the technique will greatly benefit from the high-energy fourth generation synchrotrons, where the same type of analysis could be performed with lower emittances and extremely brilliant sources by using even shorter wavelengths, acquisition times and superior spatial resolutions.

Acknowledgement

G.M.-C. acknowledges the funding by the Spanish Ministry of Innovation, Science, and Technology and the Spanish Ministry of Economy through Research Project RTI2018-097195-B-I00. In addition, the funding from European Union QUANTIMONY project within Horizon 2020 MSCA research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 860110 is acknowledged.

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